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Increasing Sales of Financial Products and Services Through Analysis of Weaknesses and Strengths

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ABSTRACT

The weaknesses and advantages of the company should be analyzed so that it becomes a strong starting point for the company in making effective and efficient decisions and to strengthen its position from existing competitors. formulation of what marketing strategies are applied by Pegadaian in increasing product sales so that they are able to compete in the market and how are the marketing strategies implemented by Pegadaian in the sales of its products and services. The results of this study are: the marketing strategy implemented by Pegadaian its marketing strategy with three important factors as the basis in the marketing concept and at the same time becomes the basis of the marketing strategy in the marketing mix, namely: consumer orientation, coordination and integration within the company and getting profits through consumer satisfaction.

Keywords: Sales; Product Excellence; Pawnshop Services

INTRODUCTION

Sharia pawn is one of the sharia financial products. Where Pawn (rahn) applies one type of agreement transaction in debts and receivables to gain the trust of creditors. The collateral still belongs to the person who pawned, but is controlled by the pawnbroker. Recognizing market characteristics and market structure is very beneficial for companies to be able to stay competitive and survive. The weaknesses and strengths of the company should be analyzed so that it becomes a strong starting point for the company in making decisions. Sharia pawnshops as a financing institution in the current era and in the future can be said to be an important and very needed institution, especially the pace of development of non-bank financial institutions engaged in debt giving services is now emerging so that it is necessary for the

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institution/company engaged in this field itself to compete with its competitors in terms of getting customers and retaining customers as one of the businesses so that The institution itself can not only make a profit but also survive [1].

The use of pawns only by the owner (Rahn) can still be debated, but the tradition of the Banjar people that Murtahin takes the results or benefits of the entire pawn is a field data that serves as a guide for the research. The contract that occurs is that the transaction is carried out not based on debts and receivables and the practice of using pawn goods which are fully the right of the pawnholder. benefits the pawnbroker, but based on the concept of fairness, the utilization of the pawn object can be divided between the pawnbroker and the pawnholder [3].

The concept of sharia pawnshop operations refers to the modern administrative system, namely the principles of rationality, efficiency and effectiveness that are aligned with Islamic values. To pay off the loan, customers only need to submit a certain amount of money and a letter of proof of rahn with a short processing time. To be able to obtain services from Sharia Pawnshops, people only need to hand over their movable assets (gold, diamonds, vehicles, and others) to be deposited [2]. Determine the estimated value of the movable goods which will be used as a benchmark for calculating the imposition of deposit rent (storage services) and the ceiling of loan money that can be given. The estimated value of goods is determined based on the intrinsic value and market price that has been set.

RESEARCH ELABORATIONS

This definition of marketing relies on the core concept which includes needs, wants, and demands. Man must first find his needs, before he fulfills them. a process involving analysis, planning, execution, and control that includes goods and services and ideas that depend on exchanges with the aim of generating satisfaction for the parties involved. In making a good marketing strategy plan, a proper analysis is needed whose process involves 3 steps in marketing, namely: Segmenting, Positioning, Targeting.

Field research in this sense is direct participation in the research location. In addition, the author also uses a type of library research. The approach used in the research is a qualitative approach. The data collection techniques used include: Literature Study. In this case, the researcher explores theories that have developed in the field of science related to the object of research. Seeking research methods and techniques in data collection to obtain a broader orientation in the selected problem and avoid unwanted duplicates. Field Study (in carrying out this field study, three forms of techniques are used, namely interview, observation, and documentation

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The level and type of needs and desires of consumers can be different from one another, which causes the choice of the opening of the business business opportunities to become more and more, the reasons for the selection or the purpose of the selection and the factors that must be considered in a business venture for each consumer are also different. In addition, STP (Segments, Targets and Positions); That is to determine which segment the market share is in and identify consumers into certain segments and identify what targets are achieved. A good image and trust in the company will make consumers entice to make repeat purchases and consumers will not turn to other companies that also offer similar products. For companies, this will make it easier to determine the right marketing policy, in line with the development of technology at this time.

Carrying out marketing concepts so that the expected profits can be realized properly. This indicates that marketing activities within the company must be coordinated and managed in a better way. The marketing concept applied is based on four pillars, namely: target market, customer needs, integrated marketing, and profitability. Consumer orientation is carried out through market segmentation. This market segment can be formed in many ways. By referring to demographics or lifestyles, market segmentation can be done. By integrating marketing programs into the intended market segments, management can better execute marketing and can use marketing resources efficiently. Market segmentation can help management in terms of channeling money and effort to the most profitable potential market, planning products that can meet market demand, determining the most effective ways of promotion, choosing advertising media, and managing the best time.

RESULTS AND DISCUSSIONS

Without promotional activities, even the marketing of quality products does not become active and it is difficult for the industry to obtain the competitive stage that is required in the market. The promotional activities implemented include: first, Advertising, through clear sponsorship through print media (news and magazines), broadcasting media (television and radio), network media (telephone, satellite, wireless), and other electronic media (sound recordings, video recordings, website pages), and exhibition media (signboards, and posters). Nowadays, customers choose internet media or websites as marketing media that will be used for marketing. Both Events and Experiences are company-sponsored activities and programs designed to create daily interactions or special-brand interactions with consumers, including arts, sports, entertainment and more. Third, Public Relations and Publicity are various programs that are directed internally to employees from companies or external consumers, other companies, governments, and the media to promote.

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Sharia pawnshops can increase sales of products and services both now and in the future, especially in the use of 4P (Product, Price, Place, and Promotion) and STP (Segmentation, Targeting, Positioning) marketing strategies. The application of the strategy applies three important factors as the basis in the marketing concept and at the same time becomes a marketing strategy in the marketing mix adhering to: Consumer Orientation (through market segmentation by focusing on: measurable, in large quantities, easily accessible, distinguishable and actionable); Coordination and Integration within the Company (through all existing marketing elements must be integrated; everyone and part within the company participates in a coordinated effort); Earning profits through consumer satisfaction (through the concept that the general purpose of a company is profit while still prioritizing consumer satisfaction).

CONCLUSIONS

Developing and realizing pawnshops that are able to survive in running their business so that they are able to increase their role in increasing profits and work productivity of their institutions are advised to improve and innovate again in developing their marketing strategies.

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